

Studies on the Colorimetric Determination of Silica in Rocks. Part II : A Rapid Method of Determination of Silica in Presence of Phosphorus

R. C. SARKAR

Analytical Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay-400 085

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A rapid differential spectrophotometric method for the determination of silica as β -silicomolybdic acid is presented for routine analysis of rocks and geological materials. After full development of the silicomolybdic acid in weakly acid medium, the solution is made strongly acid resulting in the destruction of the colour due to phosphomolybdic acid, the former remaining unaffected. As the intrinsic instability of the β -isomer precludes the use of silica standard as a reference solution, potassium chromate solution is preferentially used for differential measurement using two silica standards to bracket the absorbance of the sample. Appreciable amounts of P, Ti, Fe(II) and low amounts of As, Ge and V commonly present in silicate rocks, do not interfere.

THE ruggedness of the colorimetric method of silica determination relying upon the formation of β -silicomolybdic acid, is evaluated in Part I of this series¹. A variety of analytical methods based on the formation of silicomolybdic acid are described and the conditions that lead to production of either α - or β -acid are studied and discussed in the literature referred to in the earlier bibliography. Interference from phosphorus is normally corrected for rather than removed by auxiliary complexing agents except in the case of the Mo-blue method. Separate determination of phosphorus is, therefore, essential for making necessary correction that really affects the rapidity of the analysis. Methods^{2,3} are suggested for the analysis of two- and three-component heteropoly acid systems making use of multiple non-aqueous extraction from solution at varied acid concentration. Heteropoly-molybdates of phosphorus and silicon in an aqueous solution are determined without separation but by choosing conditions under which a single component could be measured in one aliquot, and the sum of the components in another⁴. Dorokhova and AlimarIn⁵ in their excellent review article on the extraction of heteropoly compounds, summarise data on the extraction of these compounds and its analytical application. It is observed⁶ that selective determination of silicon in presence of phosphorus, arsenic and germanium can be accomplished by making the final solution strongly acid. Ohlweiler and Meditsch⁷ make the solution strongly acid to 3*N* in HCl after developing 12-molybdosilicic acid in order to discharge the colour due to phosphorus before extracting the former with MIBK for the indirect titrimetric determination of silica.

In the present work a rapid differential spectrophotometric method of determination of silica in rocks containing phosphorus, iron(II) and titanium is described. The proposed method is considerably simpler than one referred to above.

Experimental

Reagents :

1. *Sodium molybdate solution* : Dissolve 7.5 g of A.R. grade $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 85 ml water in a polythene beaker and add 15.0 ml of (1+5) H_2SO_4 . Filter and store the solution in a polythene bottle.
2. Prepare the other reagents as given earlier¹.

Procedure* :

(a) *Preparation of solutions* : Fuse 95-130 mg of ground and dried sample and the standard (not more than 70 mg SiO_2) for 10 min with the residue obtained on drying 5.0 ml of 30% NaOH in a Ni-crucible and dissolve the melt with water following the steps described earlier¹. Transfer the contents of the crucible into a 500 ml polythene beaker containing 350 ml water and 15.0 ml of (1+5) H_2SO_4 and mix. Transfer the mixture into a 500 ml standard flask and make up the volume with water.

*In the procedure described above, follow the details described in reference 1.

(b) *Colour development and differential measurement :*

1. Take 20 ml (2-3 mg SiO₂) of the sample solution and suitable aliquots of the standard silica solution into 100 ml volumetric flasks.
2. Add a few drops of 0.05N-KMnO₄ to give a light purple colour to the solution in each flask.
3. Dilute the solution to about 60 ml with water.
4. Add 10.0 ml of sodium molybdate solution into one of the flasks, mix, and keep for 10 min.
5. Add 20 ml of (1+2.6) H₂SO₄, make upto 100 ml with water, and mix.
6. After five min measure the absorbance of the solution at 400 nm against a suitable reference solution prepared by diluting 0.005M-K₂CrO₄ with 0.1M-(NH₄)₂HPO₄ (1).
7. Add 10 ml of the molybdate solution to other flasks one by one after a convenient interval and follow the steps 5 and 6.
8. Measure the absorbance of the compensating solution with all reagents except molybdate against the blank solution with the same reagents to correct for any residual absorbances of the respective sample solution.

Results and Discussion

The silica content is obtained from the expression, $\%SiO_2 = \left[L + (H - L) \times \frac{aX - aL}{aH - aL} \right] \times \frac{100}{W}$, where L and H are the amounts of SiO₂ in the aliquots of the low and the high standards, and W is the amount of sample in the aliquot taken for colour development, and aL, aH and aX are the respective absorbances. To ensure better accuracy, (i) a fixed time lag should be adhered to for a given set of measurements, (ii) the absorbance of any sample should be closely straddled by the absorbances of two silica standards and (iii) the aliquots of the sample and the standard solutions, should be equalised by the addition of the required volume of the reagent blank solution.

In this work the β -silicomolybdic acid is developed at a pH around 1.5 and at a molybdate concentration of about 0.04M. This condition is favourable for the formation of coloured heteropoly molybdates of phosphorus, arsenic, germanium and vanadium (if present) which interfere with the silica determination. The absorbances of the colour due to arsenic and germanium are very low at 400 nm. Besides, these elements as well as vanadium are normally present in the silicate rocks at very low concentrations and their negligible effect on the silica determination, is ignored. The colour due to phosphorus (also arsenic and germanium) after its full development in weakly acid solution is destroyed by making the test solution strongly acid to about 2N-H₂SO₄. In a separate study involving the determination of SiO₂ at a concentration of 6.3 mg/l at least up to 5.6 mg P₂O₅/l could be tolerated. In this study in

which the concentration of P₂O₅ was changed from 2.2-5.6 mg/l and in which the acidity was changed from 1.6-2.3 N-H₂SO₄, the observed precision of a single determination was less than 0.4%. To avoid the formation of coloured chlorocomplexes HCl is not used. The relative standard deviation of the method for the concentration range 40-70% SiO₂ is found to be 0.6-0.3%. A few standard rock samples containing P₂O₅ and TiO₂ are analysed for silica by this method with comparable result (Table 1). It is warranted that the determination of phosphorus in presence of silicon, is feasible by this method for material with P/Si ratio

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF STANDARD ROCK SAMPLES

Standard Sample	% P ₂ O ₅	% TiO ₂	% SiO ₂	
			Expected	Found by Present method
GSP-1	0.23	0.66	67.38 ⁽⁸⁾	67.32
SY-3	0.54	0.15	59.68 ⁽⁹⁾	59.43
AGV-1	0.49	1.04	59.00 ⁽⁸⁾	59.40
B-1	0.41	2.40	50.40	50.60
MRG-1	0.08	3.77	39.24 ⁽⁹⁾	39.17

The P₂O₅ and TiO₂ values are taken from the corresponding references in parantheses under column 4.

being higher than that which normally occurs in the silicate rocks with an additional operation to measure the sum of the absorbances of phosphorus and silicon in another aliquot, the pH of which is maintained at around 1.5.

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